

An Unusual Case of Renal Infiltration in Chronic Lymphocytic Leukemia

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1. ABSTRACT

Chronic Lymphocytic Leukemia (CLL) is the most prevalent leukemia in adults, characterized by the monoclonal proliferation of mature B cells in the blood, bone marrow, and lymphoid tissues. While CLL primarily affects the hematopoietic system, lymph nodes, extra-nodal involvement is rare. Particularly renal involvement is very rare and poses diagnostic and therapeutic challenges. Several differentials for renal failure in a CLL patient include Sepsis, dehydration, Tumor Lysis Syndrome (TLS), extrinsic compression of the ureter by the lymph node enlargement, side effects of the cancer therapy, most uncommon being the renal involvement of the CLL. We report a case of CLL with renal infiltration leading to florid renal failure, discussing its clinical presentation, diagnostic workup, and management.

This manuscript is based on work previously presented as an abstract at the SOHO 2024 conference. The findings and conclusions outlined herein expand upon the thesis presented in that abstract.

2. KEYWORDS: Chronic lymphocytic leukemia; Renal infiltration; Venetoclax; Monoclonal B cells; Renal biopsy

3. INTRODUCTION

Sub optimal renal function in patients with CLL can have a big impact on their health and survival. Common differentials which can lead to poor renal function in patients with CLL are, Sepsis, dehydration, Tumor lysis syndrome, extrinsic compression of the ureter by the lymph node enlargement, side effects of the cancer therapy, most uncommon being the renal involvement of the CLL [1,2].

A study by Strati and Shanafelt found that about 7.5% of CLL patients had kidney issues when they were diagnosed at the Mayo Clinic. Patients with kidney problems at the start tended to be older, male, and have more advanced CLL [3]. They were also less likely to get certain treatments and more likely to get others. During

follow-up, about 16% of patients experienced acute kidney injury, which was linked to factors like age, gender, and specific CLL characteristics.

Another study from the Mayo Clinic showed that kidney disease in CLL patients was linked to worse outcomes, like lower overall survival rates [2]. This means that having kidney problems can affect how doctors treat patients and what options they have for clinical trials. However, because CLL is an indolent disease, common in elderly population who have poor baseline renal function, patients rarely get kidney biopsies. In fact, in the study by Strati P, et al. [2] only about 1.2% of CLL patients got kidney biopsies [2]. This lack of biopsy data makes it harder to fully understand the reasons for sub optimal renal function in the CLL patients.

4. CASE PRESENTATION

A Patient is a 67-year-old female with a history of relapsed Chronic Lymphocytic Leukemia (CLL) initially diagnosed in 2012. CLL is characterized by Trisomy 12, unmutated IGVH, and positive markers including Zap 70 and CD38. The patient was asymptomatic on diagnosis, was under surveillance until 2019. Initial treatment with Ibrutinib and Rituximab was given from April 2019 to May 2022 as she started experiencing fatigue, rapid lymphocyte doubling time, and thrombocytopenia. However, in April 2022, she developed acute kidney injury, with a peak creatinine level of 3.5, initial work up includes tumor lysis labs which were negative, CT scan of the Abdomen and Pelvis was unremarkable with no extrinsic or intrinsic obstruction noted on the renal drainage system. Renal biopsy was pursued as a further investigative step revealing extensive diffuse lymphoid infiltration of the kidney by monoclonal B cells consistent with CLL and 2nd review of pathology was done at the Mayo Clinic, confirming the Renal infiltration of the CLL.

Subsequently, the treatment regimen was switched to Venetoclax and Obinutuzumab from June 29, 2022. She completed six cycles of Obinutuzumab by November 17, 2022, and continued Venetoclax with good tolerance until August 2023, with return of the renal function to creatinine of 1.6 which is her baseline creatinine.

The patient remains asymptomatic currently, prompting surveillance by Hematology and Nephrology being off Venetoclax per current guidelines [4]. Laboratory monitoring with CBC, CMP monthly, flow cytometry quarterly. Avoiding use of nephrotoxic medications and encouraging adequate hydration.

If renal function worsens post-Venetoclax discontinuation, resumption of therapy is being considered.

5. DISCUSSION

Renal involvement in CLL is uncommon, occurring in less than 5% of cases, and typically presents with non-specific symptoms such as fatigue and renal dysfunction. Diagnosis often requires renal biopsy, revealing lymphoid infiltration like ours. CLL being an indolent disease, not all patients need to be treated. **Table 1** defines various indications of treatment in patients with CLL, Renal failure when noted in a patient with CLL should be thoroughly evaluated to rule out differentials like Sepsis, dehydration, nephrotoxic medication use, tumor lysis syndrome, with help of through history, exam, medication review, basic blood work to check for electrolytes if the basic work up does not reveal the cause of renal failure, further investigation with imaging is necessary and Nephrology consultation is also required as many of the cancer therapies have a comprehensive list of side effects which needs a multidisciplinary approach. CLL renal infiltration is very rare, accurate incidence is ill defined, as the number of patients who received renal biopsies as part of the CLL work up is low

historically, as it is very difficult to discern given baseline CKD in elderly population with CLL. Hence it should be considered in the list of differentials and appropriate work up with renal biopsy is required to make the diagnosis. Once proven that renal failure is secondary to CLL, appropriate treatment must be initiated.

Prior to treatment initiation FISH profiling of the tumor is necessary for risk stratification. Based on the presence or absence of del (17p)/TP53 mutation stratify the agents of choice used for the treatment of CLL. Our case was negative for (17p)/TP53 mutation upon the FISH testing. **Table 1** lists the first line treatment choices for low and intermediate risk. This list is constantly evolving as there is a tremendous amount of research that's ongoing on patients with CLL. When our patient got started on the treatment Ibrutinib + Rituximab [5] was the preferred combination of choice, but down the lane, as she got diagnosed with renal infiltration of the CLL, Venetoclax + Obinutuzumab mab [6] became a category 1 combination (**Figure 1**).

Table 1: Indications for Treatment in CLL.

Indications for treatment in CLL	First line preferred Tx options (Category 1)	Other preferred choices
Fatigue, drenching night sweats, unintentional weight loss >10% of body weight over previous 6 months, fever without infection	Acalabrutinib +/- Obinutuzumab	Ibrutinib (Category 1)
Threatened organ function	Venetoclax +/- Obinutuzumab	Ibrutinib + Obinutuzumab (Category 2B)
Progressive symptomatic or bulky disease (spleen >6cm below coastal margin, lymph nodes >10cm)	Zanubritinib	Ibrutinib + Rituximab (Category 2B)
Progressive thrombocytopenia, progressive anemia, steroid refractory autoimmune cytopenias		Ibrutinib + Venetoclax (Category 2B)

Figure 1: Showing treatment response over months.

Management of CLL in patients with renal dysfunction can be of challenge, given the high risk for TLS and the requiring dose reductions of the cancer therapy [7], frequent monitoring of CMP, uric acid, and aggressive support from nephrology colleagues and along with the use of prophylactic Allopurinol. A meticulous medication review with the help of a pharmacist is required to avoid drug interactions [8]. Although most CLL medications aren't known to harm the kidneys, some like Venetoclax and ibrutinib were the most linked to Acute Kidney Injury (AKI). However, newer-generation Bruton Tyrosine Kinase Inhibitors (BTKi) have fewer kidney-related side effects compared to Ibrutinib.

The precise reasons behind AKI and other kidney issues with these drugs aren't entirely clear, but there have been reports of acute interstitial nephritis with ibrutinib, as well as a notable association between ibrutinib and hypertension, which can persist despite treatment. Adhering to strict dosing protocols and promptly addressing any side effects is crucial for ensuring safe and effective treatment outcomes.

6. CONCLUSION

In CLL, renal failure can be a consequence of tumor infiltration, glomerular diseases, electrolyte imbalances, and treatment-related toxicities. With the advent of more targeted therapies for CLL, the risk of TLS (tumor lysis syndrome) becomes a crucial consideration, requiring proactive preventive measures. In clinical practice, both hematologists and nephrologists must be well-versed the various differentials leading to sub optimal renal function in patients with CLL, although uncommon renal infiltration of CLL is worth working up for in cases of

inconclusive non interventional work up as it might indicate disease recurrence/progression prompting the treatment change or resumption and with the advent of advanced cancer therapies it can be reversible if caught early and treated cautiously.

7. REFERENCES

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